

Reply to Mary Beard observation regarding my research work on Julius Caesar profile

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Here is given a discussion of my scientific research on Julius Caesar's profile, in reply to a note in M. Beard's book entitled 'Twelve Caesars', 2021. Because of the formulation of her note, my reply is strictly necessary.

Torino, July 22, 2023.

Today, July 22, 2023, I found that an article of mine, about Julius Caesar's profile as depicted on coins and in marble busts, had been mentioned in a book by M. Beard, entitled 'Twelve Caesars: Images of Power from the Ancient World to the Modern', 2021. In a note of this book, it is told the following: "A rather rough and shaggy reconstruction of Caesar's face, a collaboration between archaeologist Tom Buijtendorp and physical anthropologist Maja d'Holloosy, was put on show at the National Antiquities Museum in Leiden: <https://www.rmo.nl/en/news-press/news/a-new-look-at-julius-caesar/>; Daily Mail 25 June 2018 ('Julius Caesar had a "crazy bulge" on his head after it was squashed during childbirth, new 3D reconstruction reveals'). Further 'scientific' attention to the Tusculum head: Sparavigna 'The Profiles'; Carotta, 'Il Cesare incognito' (using the head to back up his eccentric belief that Julius Caesar was Jesus Christ!)" (Beard, 2021)

I thank Beard for reporting my work, however, since she has mentioned it as a 'further 'scientific' attention' between a 'rough and shaggy' reconstruction and an 'eccentric' point of view, I am inevitably forced to explain my scientific research in greater detail, to avoid any possible misunderstanding.

My article is entitled "The Profiles of Caesar's Heads given by Tusculum and Pantelleria Marbles", 2018. Before the explanation of the biometric approach to Caesar's profiles, some words must be added about the works made by the other persons mentioned in the Beard's note. About Buijtendorp and d'Holloosy reconstruction, I discussed in 2018 questioning the method (reconstruction from two marble busts and wrong proportions). In particular, the researchers mixed two marble busts, the Tusculum bust held in Torino and one of the two Julius Caesar busts held in Leiden. Torino and Leiden busts has different biometric ratios.

For what is concerning Francesco Carotta's 'eccentric belief', he published in 2005 a book entitled 'Jesus was Caesar: on the Julian origin of Christianity'. His theory regards historical Jesus as based on the Gospels revised in the framework of the roman model of deified Caesar cult. Carotta's work about the Tusculum bust - anatomy and volumes, the possibility that it was a part of a statuary group representing Endymion and Selene myth -, is detailed in https://www.carotta.de/subseite/texte/articula/Sulla_postura_del_Cesare_Tuscolo.pdf.

For what is regarding my biometric method, and therefore my 'scientific' approach, it is necessary to stress that my attention to the roman portraiture metric approach was stimulated by a RAI Broadcaster program, where Alberto Angela, world-wide reputed researcher, explained with a compass and a marble bust, how profile angular measurements (forehead - nose - chin) were used to prepare a roman emperor head's model. From the model, several marble copies were sent to all roman sites of the empire, to have faithful portraits of the emperor. Today, dentistry is using biometric measurements to fit the Vertical Dimension of Occlusion (VDO), for denture and implantology. "VDO of the patient remained unchanged. We used a compass for

measuring two times the distance between the tip of the nose and the mandibular symphysis.” (Gargari et al., 2013). Therefore, it is not ‘rough’, shaggy¹ or ‘eccentric’ to suppose that ancient romans made biometric measurements for emperors’ portraitures. This is true not only for busts, but also for coins. Coins were the only available method at the time to identify a person from his/her profile. “In the ensuing imperial period, the portrait of the ruler became a fixture on Roman coins. Depictions of the emperor and other members of the ruling dynasty were designed to represent their truest possible likeness without embellishment or even any kind of idealization” ([Deutsche Bundesbank](#)). In my “Comparing the Profiles of Caesar's Heads Given by the Pantelleria Marble Bust and by a Coin of 44 BC”, I considered the biometric approach for profiles on coins and marble busts.

For reader’s convenience, here the contents of my two articles. The first is that mentioned by Beard.

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The Profiles of Caesar's Heads given by Tusculum and Pantelleria Marbles

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✓ July 17, 2018 (v1) Working paper Open Access

Comparing the Profiles of Caesar's Heads given by the Pantelleria Marble Bust and by a Coin of 44 BC

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Tusculum and Pantelleria busts

Abstract: Here we want to show a comparison of the profiles of Julius Caesar’s head, as portrayed in Tusculum and in Pantelleria marbles. These profiles are in good agreement and are in good agreement to that given in a coin of 44 BC, struck one month before Caesar’s assassination. Written in Torino, 18 July 2018. Submitted ZENODO. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1314696

As told by Flemming S. Johansen (Getty Publications, 1987), the Tusculum portrait is one of the two main types of Julius Caesar’s portraitures, alongside the Chiaramonti bust. The Tusculum head is dated to 50–40 BC and today is housed in the permanent collection of the Museo d'Antichità in Turin, Italy. The Tusculum head is also known as the “Tusculum bust”, however the term “bust” is not properly used because we have only the head, whereas a bust is a sculpture of a person's head, shoulders, and chest.

The Caesar’s head was found by Lucien Bonaparte in Tusculum. With some other items of Bonaparte's collection, the bust passed to the House of Savoy and was taken to the Castle of Agliè. A century and a half later, in 1940, archaeologist Maurizio Borda, comparing the profile with some coins, recognized that Caesar was portrayed in it (Getty Publications, 1987, Carotta, 2016). Borda considered the Tusculum portrait an original from Caesar’s last years, but, according to Johansen, it is a copy after a bronze original made shortly before or after the death of Caesar (let me note that I am not able to explain how Johansen concluded the existence of a bronze statue). The scholar noted also that it is possible that the Tusculum bust was made after the death of Caesar. In Getty Publications, Johansen tells that the Tusculum portrait type exists in three other copies which we can find at Woburn Abbey, England, in Florence and in Rome. However, in 1903, Frank J. Scott told about the Woburn Abbey bust the following. "A life-size bust, said to resemble one of the busts formerly in the Roman gallery of the Louvre, now withdrawn to the "Magasins"! Bernoulli pronounces it modern." So, it is better to consider the Tusculum bust with Florence and Rome busts, and use, instead of the

¹ Shaggy: what does it mean? Cambridge dictionary tells that it means “having or covered with long, rough, and untidy hair, or (of hair) long, rough, and untidy”: a little bit ironic for our bald-headed Julius Caesar.

Woburn Abbey bust, the recently discovered Pantelleria bust, dated from the period between the reigns of Tiberius and Claudius (Hekster, 2015, Corazzi, 2017), that is, from the first half of the first century AD.

It was in 2003 that this perfect face of Julius Caesar had been found in the Italian island of Pantelleria (Owen, 2003). Sebastiano Tusa, Thomas Schaefer (Tubingen University) and Massimo Osanna (Università della Basilicata) discovered the Caesar's head with other two marble heads of Titus and Agrippina. The perfectly preserved white marble bust found in Pantelleria is putting Caesar in a new light, according to these archaeologists, because this portrait is considered as more pristine than the other contemporary marble busts of Caesar known to exist (Owen, 2003).

Of this marble head, of the Tusculum head and of their comparison to other busts, we discussed previously (Sparavigna, 2012, 2013, Corazzi & Sparavigna, 2013, Sparavigna, 2018). In particular, in “Comparing the Profiles of Caesar's Heads given by the Pantelleria Marble Bust and by a Coin of 44 BC”, we have discussed the profile of the Pantelleria head compared to that of a coin of 44 BC, struck in the occasion of the Lupercalia, one month before Caesar's assassination (Macquarie University) (about Lupercalia, see Brown, 1973, Vuković, 2016). The comparison shows a remarkable agreement. Here, we want to stress another remarkable agreement, that between the profiles of Tusculum and Pantelleria heads. For the comparison, we use the pictures in the Figure 1. On the left, the Tusculum bust and, on the right, the Pantelleria bust.

Figure 1. Profiles of Tusculum and Pantelleria (Images are used here just for scientific and cultural purposes). From the left: right side, front view, left side of the Tusculum bust. Left side of the Pantelleria bust.

About the Tusculum bust, we must tell that the head is not symmetric. The reason is well explained by Francesco Carotta in his discussion on the posture of the head (Carotta, 2016). According to Carotta, in origin the head was not in the vertical position as we see it today. Some anomalies displayed by the head are due to its artistic rendering, required in the case that it had to be seen from below. After his analysis, Carotta concluded that the Tusculum head was a part of a statue and that, on this statue, the head had not a vertical position for sure (Carotta, 2016). This is also clear from the different position of the ears in the Figure 1: the head of Tusculum was placed with a direction inclined towards the right shoulder.

The artist that made the Pantelleria head was well aware of such a rendering of the Tusculum head (certainly he had seen it or even the bronze original). As a consequence, probably for making a Caesar's bust, the artist made the Pantelleria head with a more vertical posture (Carotta, 2016). However, also in this case, the posture is not perfectly vertical. To compare the portraits of Tusculum and Pantelleria, and to compare them to a coin, we use the left side of the faces because it seems more conveniently rendered. It is true that, normally, slight differences exist between the sides of a head, but, since the left part of these heads is that which is having a posture closer to that of the coins, we will use it even if the coins are supposed to show the right side of the head. Let us note also the following: if we see in a coin a head turned to the right, this does not necessarily

mean that we are looking at the right side of the portrayed person. In the case of a Buca Denarius for instance, it was the left side of the head to be portrayed but reproduced after a mirror reflection to turn it to the right (Francesco Carotta, private communication). Therefore, to compare the profiles in the Figure 1, and for a further comparison to coins, I turn them all in the same direction. I use the filter of GIMP for an edge detection too. The result is given in the Figure 2.

Figure 2. From the left: profiles of Tusculum (right side), Pantelleria (left side), and Tusculum (left side). The images are given after an edge detection filtering with GIMP.

Figure 3. The edges of the profiles superimposed (left side of both heads). The Pantelleria bust is given in white and the Tusculum bust in black.

From the Figure 3, where we have used the left side of both heads, we can see that we have a quite good agreement between the profiles. Even the position of the ear is rather close.

As previously told, we have shown in Sparavigna, July 17, 2018, that the Pantelleria bust is in strong agreement with a coin struck in 44 BC, before the Caesar's assassination. Here a figure from the previous work is given for reader's convenience.

Figure 4: Distances are given by the number of pixels between the end points (Images of coin and bust are used here just for scientific and cultural purposes).

If we use the Figure 4 to make some measurements, we find that differences are very small, less than 3%. The posterior part of the head is different, but this is due to the fact that a crescent was inserted between the frame of the coin and the wreathed head. Since from the Figure 3 we can see the profiles of Tusculum and Pantelleria heads almost coincident, let us investigate and compare the profile of the Tusculum bust and of the coin of Lupercalia too. The result is given in the Figure 5.

Figure 5: On the left, the coin of 44 BC, struck one month before Caesar's assassination. On the right, the profile of the Tusculum bust. In the middle the two images mixed. Again, the agreement is remarkably good.

Figure 6: In blue, the profile of the coin and in red the profile of the statue. The only difference is in the lower part of the nose. Please note that ears are coincident.

From the Figures 5 and 6, we can tell that the agreement is remarkably good. Only the lower part of the nose is slightly different. Please note also that the ears are almost coincident.

We could use for comparison other coins too, but this is beyond the aim of the paper, which is that of the analysis of Tusculum and Pantelleria profiles. The most important result of this work is that the profiles of the two marble portraits are close to that depicted in a coin struck when Caesar was alive, in occasion of the Lupercalia of 44 BC.

Pantelleria Marble Bust and a Coin of 44 BC

Abstract: Here we want to show an interesting fact concerning the profile of the Caesar's head, which is portrayed in the Pantelleria marble bust. It is the same of the portrait of Caesar given by a coin of 44 BC. The coin was struck just after Caesar's refusal of the crown offered by Mark Antony during the Lupercalia. Written in Torino, 17 July 2018. Submitted ZENODO. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1313808

As previously told by Owen, in 2003 a perfect face of Julius Caesar had been found in the Italian island of Pantelleria. Sebastiano Tusa, Thomas Schaefer (Tubingen University) and Massimo Osanna (Università della Basilicata) discovered the Caesar's head with other two marble heads of Titus and Agrippina. ... Here, we want to note an interesting fact concerning the Pantelleria head. We compare it to a portrait of Caesar given by a coin of 44 BC. The profiles of the Pantelleria bust and of the head in the coin are the same. As explained by the Macquarie University, the coin was struck just after Caesar's refusal of the crown offered by Mark Antony during the Lupercalia (North, 2008). Lupercalia was a very ancient annual festival, observed in Rome on February 15, to avert the evil spirits and purify the city (Brown, 1973). Lupercalia was also called "dies Februatus", purified (literally "februated day") after the fumes of purification (see the etymology at the link <https://www.etymonline.com/word/february>).

The Lupercalia had its own priesthood, the Luperci. They were young men forming two religious collegia based on ancestry: the Quinctiliani (named after gens Quinctia) and the Fabiani (named after gens Fabia). Each college was headed by a magister. In 44 BC, a third college, the Juliani, was instituted in honour of Julius Caesar, and its first magister was Mark Antony (Vuković, 2016). The college of Juliani disbanded during civil wars and was not reestablished in the reforms of Augustus. Descriptions of the Lupercalia of 44 BC tell that during this festival Julius Caesar refused three times a golden crown offered to him by Mark Antony.

In the Figure 7 we see, in the up/left panel, the Caesar's head in the coin struck just after Lupercalia and in the down/right panel the profile of the marble head of Pantelleria. The up/right and down/left panels are giving the two images mixed in different percentage. We can see a remarkable agreement of the two profiles.

Figure 7. Profiles are the same (Images of coin and bust are used here just for scientific and cultural purposes).

Figure 8 (the same as Fig.4): Distances are given by the number of pixels between the end points (Images of coin and bust are used here just for scientific and cultural purposes).

From the Figure 7, it seems that even the position of the ear is the same. Therefore, let us measure the lengths of the three segments given in the Figure 8. Differences are very small, less than 3%. The posterior part of the head is different, but this is due to the fact that a crescent was inserted between the frame of the coin and the wreathed head. After Figures 7 and 8, a possible conclusion could be the following. The Pantelleria portraiture was made according to this coin, which was struck when Caesar was alive, one month before his assassination. As a consequence, the Pantelleria bust could be considered as one of the most faithful rendering of Caesar's head.

Beard's opinion about Tusculum bust

At the beginning of my discussion, I reported note number 37 of the second chapter of Beard's book. In this chapter, the Tusculum bust is mentioned. It is strictly necessary to consider specifically Beard words to understand the framework of the note.

“In the early years of the nineteenth century, Lucien Bonaparte—archaeologist, collector, sometime revolutionary and younger (partly estranged) brother of Napoleon— discovered a marble head in excavations near his house just south of Rome, on the site of the ancient town of Tusculum. ... After Bonaparte hit hard times both politically and economically, it ended up in the hands of new owners in a castle at Aglié outside Turin, where it remained anonymously for a hundred years or so. It was only in 1940 (an auspicious moment for discovering Caesars in Italy, given Mussolini's enthusiasm) that an Italian archaeologist, Maurizio Borda, argued that it was in fact Julius Caesar (Fig. 2.7)” (Beard, 2021). Let me note that Mussolini's propaganda, involving Caesar and Augustus, started *before* 1940. I suggest reading Syme, 2002, Favale, 2012, and Mazza, 2017.

Fig.9 : Let us use the coin of August 43 BC. AR Denarius 43 BC. Rome mint. L Flaminius Chilo. Laureate head right within pelleted border. From a picture of the profile of the Tusculum bust, we can obtain a silhouette (in red). Superposing to the coin, we have a remarkable coincidence ([Sparavigna, Sunday, July 15, 2018](#)).

“This was on the usual grounds of the similarities to the coin portraits of 44 BCE, but Borda went further. Not only did he conclude that the similarities were so close that the portrait must have been made during Caesar’s lifetime, but he also felt able to use the sculpture to diagnose two deformations of the skull from which Caesar had obviously suffered” (Beard, 2021). I suppose Beard is using adverb “obviously” referring to Borda’s point of view. For what is regarding the coins, “il Borda prese a paragone una moneta del Mettius [44 BC], la Simon un’altra del Buca” (Carotta, 2016). In the Figure 9, I am showing another comparison, with Chilo denarius, 43 BC. In the Figure 5, I used the Lupercalia coin (a Buca coin, 44 BC).

“The slightly odd shape of the head was not caused by incompetence, or idiosyncrasy, on the part of the artist. It was an accurate reflection of two congenital cranial pathologies, clinocefalia (a slight depression at the top of the head) and plagiocefalia (a flattening on one side of the skull).” (Beard, 2021). To understand the appearance of clinocefalia and plagiocefalia, see please the figures, from Fig.11, in F. Carotta, 2016, https://www.carotta.de/subseite/texte/articula/Sulla_postura_del_Cesare_Tuscolo.pdf

“But, even more than its British Museum rival, the Tusculum head has been considered to be so close to life that it could support a clinical diagnosis: this is not just looking Caesar in the eye, it is taking his case notes. Here too views have begun to change. The Caesar from Tusculum still has its enthusiasts, and in 2018 it was used—with much international media attention—to produce a full-scale, ‘scientific’ reconstruction of the authentic face of the dictator.³⁷” (Beard, 2021).

And here we find the note ³⁷ and the mention to ‘scientific’ reconstruction. Let us repeat: “A rather rough and shaggy reconstruction of Caesar’s face, a collaboration between archaeologist Tom Buijtendorp and physical anthropologist Maja d’Hollosy. ... Further ‘scientific’ attention to the Tusculum head: Sparavigna ‘The Profiles’; Carotta, ‘Il Cesare incognito’ (using the head to back up his eccentric belief that Julius Caesar was Jesus Christ!)” (Beard, 2021). My research, that is the ‘further ‘scientific’ attention to the Tusculum head’, as teased by Beard, was regarding the biometric measures for comparison of Lupercalia coin (44 BC), Tusculum and Pantelleria busts. I *never* draw any conclusion about Caesar’s health or supported clinical diagnoses. My discussion was about the profiles and the angular distances about relevant structures of human face, to argue about a biometric method used by romans in portraiture. Moreover, I *never* mentioned Jesus Christ in my studied about roman portraiture. Therefore, the reference to my work as given by Beard in her note can turn out in a wrong information regarding my scientific research.

I continued investigation in “Profiles of Julius Caesar's Heads: A Biometric Approach”, August 2018, and in “Biometric Portraits of Emperors on the Roman Coins”, August 2018. Since Beard is mentioning also the Caesar Rhone bust, besides the Pantelleria bust, let me show it as I proposed in August 2018 in the “Profiles of Julius Caesar’s Heads”.

Figure 10. Profiles of marble heads (Tusculum, Pantelleria, Farnese collection and Arles) of Julius Caesar. Images of the busts are used here just for scientific and cultural purposes. Distances are given in numbers of pixels. For image credits and for other profiles, see please “Profiles of Julius Caesar's Heads”.

To conclude, let me stress the fundamental discovery by Giuseppe Ceraudo, Università del Salento, and his team of a Julius Caesar bust in Aquinum (Ceraudo, 2019). This is a bust of Pantelleria type. Here in the following the morphing of marble.

Figure 11: From left to right, the morphing of the marble from Aquinum to Pantelleria bust.

Post scriptum, 23 July.

In 2012, I wrote a proposal for 3D analysis of Julius Caesar busts (Arles, Tusculum, Farnese). I wrote: “Until June 25 of this year [2012], the ancient history of Arles is the subject of an exhibition at the Louvre Museum of Paris. The Museum is hosting several Roman pieces recovered from the river Rhone. One of these roman artifacts is the Arles portrait bust, a life-sized marble bust, which is the portrait of a man with wrinkles and several other realistic details. Some divers discovered this bust during an archaeological survey in the waters of the river of Arles. It seems that the realism of this portrait is in agreement with the features of plastic art of the late Republican period, that is, of the first century BCE. This bust was therefore proposed as a portrait of Julius Caesar. If it is dated about 46 BCE, this could be the oldest known representation of Caesar [\[link\]](#). However, *Mary Beard, professor of Classics, remarked the need of further research for identifying the man as Caesar* [Beard, 2008]. In fact, Reference [Beard, 2008] is shortly outlining how we can identify the person portrayed in a newly discovered artifact by comparing it with the images of books. In particular, she is telling that the collections of coins are quite useful. Accordingly, ...”

The title of Beard’s article is “The face of Julius Caesar? Come off it!” Very doubtfully, about Arles bust and the related archaeological research Beard wrote: “The game of art-historical snap is a risky business, ... There is nothing at all to suggest that it came from 49-46 BC. The *desperate archaeologist* in this case has, of course, found a nice reason for imagining how a made-from-life portrait of Julius Caesar might have ended up at the bottom of the Rhone. It was chucked there after Caesar had been assassinated and so had fallen from favour” (Beard, 2008). In Beard’s article, it is not mentioned the name of the archaeologist that found the bust in Rhone River, being just dubbed as “desperate archaeologist”. The name is Luc Long, DRASSM, French Department of Underwater Archaeology.

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